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Van der Waals heteroepitaxy of air stable quasi-free standing silicene layers on CVD epitaxial graphene/6H-SiC

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ABSTRACT

Graphene, consisting of an inert, thermally stable material with an atomically flat, dangling bond-free surface is by essence an ideal template layer for van der Waals heteroepitaxy of two-dimensional materials such as silicene. However, depending on the synthesis method and growth parameters, graphene (Gr) substrates could exhibit, on a single sample, various surface structures, thicknesses, defects, and steps heights. These structures noticeably affect the growth mode of epitaxial layers, e.g. turning the layer-by-layer growth into the Volmer

Weber growth promoted by defect-assisted nucleation. In this work, the growth of silicon on CVD epitaxial Gr (1 ML Gr/1ML Gr buffer) on 6H-SiC substrate is investigated by a combination of AFM, STM, XPS, and Raman spectroscopy measurements. It is shown that the perfect control of full-scale defect-free 1 ML Gr with a single surface structure and the ultra-clean conditions for MBE deposition of silicon represent key prerequisites for ensuring the growth of extended silicene sheets on (6x6)Gr/6H-SiC. At low coverages, the deposition of Si produces large silicene sheets (some hundreds of nanometers large) attested by both AFM and SEM observations and the onset of a Raman peak at 560cm^{-1} very close to the theoretical value of 570cm^{-1} calculated for free-standing silicene. This vibration mode at 560cm^{-1} represents the highest ever experimentally measured value and is representative of quasi-free standing silicene with almost no interaction with non-metal substrates. From a coverage rate of 1ML, the silicene sheets disappear at the expense of 3D Si dendritic islands whose density, size, and thickness increase with the deposited thickness. From this coverage, the Raman mode assigned to quasi-free standing silicene totally vanishes, and the 2D flakes of silicene are no longer observed by AFM. The experimental results are in total agreement with the results of kinetic Monte-Carlo simulations that rationalize the initial flake growth in solid-state dewetting conditions, followed by the growth of ridges surrounding and covering the 2D flakes. A full description of the growth mechanism is given. This study, which covers a wide range of growth parameters, challenges recent results stating the impossibility to grow silicene on a carbon inert surface and paves the way for large scale silicene growth. It definitely shows that silicene growth can only be achieved using perfectly controlled and ultra-clean deposition conditions and a defect-free Gr substrate.

INTRODUCTION

Silicene (Si-ene) represents an ideal 2D material that shares all the outstanding characteristics of graphene (mainly magnetic, mechanical, optical and electrical properties)¹⁻⁷ associated with the additional advantage of a narrow band gap that can easily be opened by doping,⁸⁻¹¹ by applying external electric and magnetic fields,^{12, 13} and mechanical strain.¹⁴ It also has the significant potential for straightforward integration into industrial semiconductor production lines, making Si-ene a promising candidate for microelectronic devices¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Si-ene has therefore attracted a large amount of studies and has been the subject of intense debates about the origin of the complex surface superstructures observed as well as its strong interaction with the substrate.²⁰⁻²⁴

The first evidence of monolayer silicon with anomalous optical properties (optical absorbance at 280 nm and photoluminescence peak at 434 nm, i.e. 2.9 eV), was given using chemical exfoliation from calcium disilicide with propylamine hydrochloride^{25, 26}. However, it was then reported that unlike Graphene (Gr), Si-ene cannot

be obtained by mechanical exfoliation.²⁷ Si-ene should then be deposited by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE)²⁸ or chemical vapor deposition (CVD).²⁹

The studies on Si-ene initially focused on its growth on Ag(001),³⁰ Ag(110),³¹ and Ag(111) substrates.^{20, 32, 33} The growth of graphene-like Si-ene nanoribbons was first reported. The demonstration of larger Si-ene sheets was then obtained by a combination of STM, angular-resolved photoemission spectroscopy, and DFT simulations.^{34, 35} However, rapidly various controversies have emerged about the origin of the various surface reconstructions observed, including (4×4) , $(\sqrt{13}\times\sqrt{13})R13.9^\circ$, $(\sqrt{7}\times\sqrt{7})R19.1^\circ$ and $(2\sqrt{3}\times 2\sqrt{3})R30^\circ$ with respect to Ag(111).^{23, 36-38}

First-principles calculations demonstrated that the linear dispersion band observed by ARPES experiments could originate from the hybridization states between silicene and Ag(111) surface.³⁹ Besides, its impressive stability was definitely ascribed to covalent bonds with the substrate.^{21, 40} It was also reported that the Dirac cone in Si-ene on a Ag(111) surface was destroyed due to the distortion of the Si-ene crystalline cell and strong band hybridization at the Si-ene/Ag(111) interface by unfolding bands.⁴¹ The linear dispersion observed in ARPES was then ascribed to the Ag substrate, instead of Si-ene.³⁹

Consequently, the investigations naturally shifted to alternative metal substrates such as Ir(111),⁴² Ru (0001),⁴³ Pt(111),⁴⁴ Pb(111),⁴⁵ and Au(111).^{46, 47} There again, strong interactions with the substrates were demonstrated both theoretically and experimentally.^{48, 49}

More recently, to overcome this limitation various experiments have been carried out on C-based inert substrates such as HOPG with hexagonal atomic arrangements.⁵⁰⁻⁵³ On this substrate, the results demonstrated that the charge modulations caused by quantum interferences (QI) serve as templates and guide the incoming Si atoms to self-assemble in 2D clusters.⁵⁴ The restricted extension of these QI limits the growth to very tiny 2D Si-ene flakes in the nanometer range and causes the transition to a 3D growth mechanism resulting in small 3D clusters at the outskirts of the tiny 2D Si-ene areas as observed experimentally.^{54, 55} The size limitation also originates from the presence of high defect densities on the HOPG substrate which favor both intercalation of silicon underneath the top surface (even at room temperature) resulting in the formation of buried silicene^{56, 57} and the preferential defect-assisted 3D cluster nucleation at the origin of the transition between layer-by-layer growth and Volmer-Weber growth.

The van der Waals (vdW) epitaxy of Si-ene layers with low-buckled honeycomb geometry on graphene-covered SiC substrates was theoretically demonstrated by first-principles calculations including vdW interaction in the ground state and quasiparticle effects in the electronic structure.⁵⁸ However, similar behavior (intercalation and 3D cluster nucleation) was also observed during the growth of silicon on graphene

epitaxially grown on Ruthenium^{59, 60} or on Ir substrates.⁶¹ At the opposite, a defect-free atomically planar graphene surface, can act as scaffold to stabilize the growth of 2D materials, enabling construction of 2D materials that do not naturally exist or are not stable as free-standing films.⁶²

To go beyond and meet the challenges raised by microelectronic devices, semiconducting MoS₂^{63, 64} and insulating h-BN⁶⁵ substrates were used for the vdW epitaxy of Si-ene. However, considering the complexity of obtaining high quality buffer layers (monocrystalline and free of defects and moirés) of MoS₂ and h-BN over large areas without crystal defects or impurities, the use of such stacked layers seems cumbersome to date for any potential applications.⁶⁶

In this work we have investigated the growth of silicon in ultra-clean Molecular Beam Epitaxy (MBE) conditions on a defect-free graphene layer obtained by an original CVD process already described elsewhere.^{67, 68} We show that two prerequisites are essential for the epitaxial growth of large scale Si-ene flakes on Gr: first, perfectly flat defect-free 1ML Gr with a single (6x6) surface structure and second the ultra-clean UHV environment during the growth of Si-ene. By a combination of AFM, STM, XPS and Raman spectroscopy measurements, we demonstrate the formation of Si-ene flakes on a scale of a few hundred nanometers randomly deposited all over the sample surface. In absence of surface defects and contaminants both on the substrate and in the deposited material, both the diffusion path toward the subsurface layer and the preferential nucleation of 3D islands are significantly reduced. Without interaction with the Gr substrate, silicon forms 2D quasi-freestanding flakes whose lateral extension reaches some hundreds of nanometers. The growth mechanism of 2D Si-ene flakes is explained by kinetic Monte-Carlo (KMC) simulations that perfectly reproduce and explain the growth morphologies resulting from 2D growth in solid-state dewetting conditions followed by the growth of 3D ridges surrounding and covering the Si-ene flakes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Graphene samples were grown on the Si-terminated face of Silicon Carbide (6H-SiC) in a horizontal hot wall CVD reactor. The 6H-SiC substrates are on-axis n-doped (nitrogen) 2'' wafers with typical thickness of ~350 μm from Tankeblue. Typical residual offsets are between 0.05 and 0.2° toward the [1-100] direction, as deduced from AFM measurements on annealed substrates under H₂.⁶⁹ Before introduction into the growth chamber, the substrates are cut into 1×1cm² pieces and then chemically cleaned with isopropanol. Graphene deposition was carried out in a horizontal CVD reactor allowing a homogeneous and reproducible deposition of Gr on the substrates, at a pressure of 800 mbar using a gas mixture of propane (C₃H₈) as the carbon source, and hydrogen (H₂) and argon (Ar) as the carrier gases. The H₂ flow ratio (H₂ flow / total flow) was set to 9%

which ensures a surface totally covered by 1ML Gr on top of the buffer layer with the $(6\sqrt{3} \times 6\sqrt{3})R30^\circ$ reconstruction (i.e. partly bonded to the SiC substrate). As we will see below, this surface structure is essential for the subsequent growth of Si-ene.

The samples completely covered with the (6x6) single surface structure are introduced into a perfectly clean UHV molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) growth chamber dedicated to Si-based heterostructures. Here, the Gr samples are first thermally cleaned at 650°C for 120 min. Then the heating is switched off and the samples are cooled down to room temperature during 180 min before silicon deposition. Silicon is deposited on the samples at room temperature using an electron beam evaporator, maintaining a constant deposition rate with uniformity of 5% on the whole sample (with sample rotation). The silicon flux was set to 0.2nm/min, which gives the best homogeneity of the deposit. The deposition time was varied between 0.2 and 1.6 min which corresponds to deposited thicknesses (θ) from 0.125ML to 6MLs.

The samples prepared in the above-mentioned way were thoroughly characterized by micro-Raman spectroscopy measurements, made using a Renishaw Invia Qotor equipped with a confocal optical microscope. A 532 nm excitation laser was employed with an excitation power of 0.5 mW and a 1800 line per millimeter grating (spectral resolution 2 cm^{-1}). The laser beam was focused onto the sample by a x100 objective with a numerical aperture NA=0.85 and a spot size of 800 nm.

Structural characterization of the samples before and after silicon deposition was investigated by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) measurements in UHV conditions using electrochemically etched tungsten tips. The UHV chamber is equipped with low energy electron diffraction (LEED), monochromatic X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS) and a STM (Omicron). STM observations were carried out at room temperature using constant current mode with $I_t = 0.3$ nA and V_t between 0.4 and 1.5 V. A photon energy of 1486.6 eV (Al-K α) for monochromatized XPS measurements was used for all samples. The photoelectrons are analyzed with an Omicron EA 125 energy analyzer. The XPS quantitative analysis of C/Si was detailed elsewhere.⁶⁸ Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained in non-contact mode in air at room temperature (Park Systems) using standard silicon cantilevers. AFM and STM data were analyzed by WSxM⁷⁰ and ImageJ software. The XPS spectra were fitted using the CasaXPS software.

RESULTS

Fig.1a shows an AFM image of the nominal Gr film on SiC (after cleaning at 650°C), where the Raman measurements in Fig. 1d were performed. The morphology presents terraces separated by a train of steps with 1.5 nm height, which mimics the regular train of 6 SiC bilayer steps of the SiC substrate. The steps are oriented

along $[1\bar{1}00]$ and are constituted of smaller sections with armchair edges, forming an angle of 120° to each other.⁶⁸ Figure 1b gives a STM high resolution image of the surface structure where the superimposition of the graphene crystalline cell (0.245 nm) and the $(6\sqrt{3} \times 6\sqrt{3})R30^\circ$ superstructure referring to $6\sqrt{3} \times \text{SiC}$ cell or $13 \times \text{Gr}$ cell ($\sim 3.2 \text{ nm}$) is clearly visible. Such a surface is called (6x6)Gr (6xSiC cell = 1.9 nm) in the rest of the manuscript (see Ref. 71 for a detailed description of graphene). The buckling of the top surface is about 0.02 – 0.04 nm in good agreement with the literature.⁷² A complete description of the surface structure and composition of (6x6)Gr can be found in Ref. 73. The sample is fully covered by very stable 1ML (6x6)Gr which is free of contaminants and defects thanks to the cleaning step. The XPS peak of carbon (C1s) gives evidence for the absence of oxygen at the surface (Fig. 1c). It can be deconvoluted into 4 different components ascribed to the buffer layer (BL) S1 (284.6 eV) and S2 (285.3 eV), to the Gr on top of the BL (284.2 eV) and to SiC below the BL (283.4 eV) that are representative of Gr on BL.^{74, 75} The quantization of the Gr coverage has been previously estimated to 1ML (from XPS analysis of the Si/C ratio).⁶⁸

Figure 1: Characterization of the nominal Gr surface after thermal cleaning at 650°C: (a) AFM and (b) STM images of the Gr surface; (c) XPS spectrum; Raman spectra in the silicon (d) and in the graphene range (e) where the D, G and 2D peaks can be observed.

The Raman spectrum of the epitaxial graphene in the silicon range is shown in Figure 1d, presenting the different Raman features of the silicon carbide substrate; for this Raman spectrum range Fig. 1e shows the three fingerprints of the electron-phonon interaction in 2D Gr, i.e. the D peak (at 1358cm^{-1}), the G peak (1591cm^{-1}) and the 2D peak (2712cm^{-1}). The D peak is ascribed to defects associated to step edge orientation in addition to other defects (atomic vacancies, dislocations, grain boundaries, step edges) of the substrate and its intensity is only related to the concentration of defects.^{76, 77} Since the D peak onset requires intervalley scattering, it cannot be produced by a perfect zigzag step edge, while it appears near a perfect armchair edge. In the present case the D/G intensity ratio is rather low. From a rough analysis of the Fig. 1e, it amounts to about 0.15, a value well lower than the ratio obtained in exfoliated Gr where it reaches values up to 0.8.⁷⁸ This means that the D peak, in the present case, could be mainly due to armchair graphene edges at SiC steps. This explains the presence of the D peak in the (6x6)Gr samples studied here that have armchair step edges. Such behavior does not apply to the 2D peak, not involving intervalley scattering, and that can be activated both by armchair and zigzag edges. The 2D peak is the second order overtone of the D peak. The graphene spectrum has a 2D peak with a single Lorentzian shape and with a full width at half-maximum $\text{FWHM}(2D) \sim 35\text{ cm}^{-1}$, a signature of single layer graphene on a SiC substrate.⁷⁹ As previously reported the graphene growth is self-limited on top of the BL/6H-SiC(0001) and produces 1ML Gr.⁶⁸ The G peak corresponds to the doubly degenerate Raman active optical vibration E_{2g} mode, where the carbon atoms oscillate in the graphene plan. The 6H-SiC exhibits various overtone peaks between 1000 to 2000 cm^{-1} with some of them superimposed to the peaks of Gr, i.e. the peak at 1514 cm^{-1} which is the overtone of the $\text{TO}(X)$ phonon at 761 cm^{-1} and the peak at 1713 cm^{-1} which is a combination of optical phonons with wave vectors near the M point at the zone edges.

Figure 2: AFM images of the surface after deposition of increasing thickness θ of silicon: (a) 0,125ML; (b) 0,25ML; (c) 0,5ML; (d) 1MLs; (e) 3MLs; and (f) 6MLs.

During the deposition (at room temperature) of silicon layers of increasing thickness from $\theta = 0.125\text{ML}$ to 6MLs at a deposition rate of 0.2 nm/min, the morphology of the surfaces changes entirely (Figure 2). The deposition of 0.125 ML results in small islands with an average diameter of $30\text{ nm} \pm 10\text{ nm}$, randomly and sparsely distributed over the surface. A more detailed observation (zoom of SEM images in Figure S1 and of AFM images in Figure S2) shows that the islands consist of two parts: a flat central area with a thickness of $\sim 0.3\text{nm} \pm 0.05\text{nm}$ and lateral dimensions about hundreds of nanometers, surrounded by small ridges with a mean height of $1.2\text{nm} \pm 0.2\text{nm}$. At increasing thickness (0.25 and 0.5ML), the size of the ridge surrounding the flat areas progressively increases (both laterally and in height) and their dendritic shape becomes more pronounced. The 2D flat central areas keep constant lateral dimensions and thickness up to a 0.5ML coverage, at which they start to be less visible, since they are partly masked by the ridges (i.e. higher dendritic islands on their edges). Since the density of the flakes increases with the deposited thickness, the overall amount of 2D material increases up to 0.5ML. After 1 ML deposition (Figure 2d), the 2D flat areas totally disappear in favor of 3D dendritic islands and the coverage rate of the surface by dendrites is about 47%. From this 1 ML coverage rate, only the growth of 3D dendrites is observed, resulting in an increase in dendrites size and height

with the deposited thickness. After 3ML deposition (Figure 2e), the surface is fully covered by dendrites, whose only thickness increases as the amount of the deposit increases up to 6MLs (Figure 2f). Scanning electron microscopy has been used to confirm the homogeneity of the deposition over the samples and their morphology (Figure S1). STM characterization (Figure S3) of the Si deposition was very complicated due to contamination of the STM tip by Si clusters. It only shows the “shadow” of dendritic island.

The elemental and chemical composition of the surface is characterized by XPS. Focus is put on Si2p and C1s peaks that are recorded at increasing deposited thicknesses of Si (Figure 3). First, it can be noted that the C1s peak remains constant throughout the growth process and regardless of the deposited thickness (Figure 3a), with the position and shape of (6x6)Gr already described above and with a similar deconvolution into 4 components (S1, S2, SiC bulk and top layer Gr). The absence of any disturbance (shift or shoulder) of this peak is a first indication of a very weak interaction of the Gr substrate with the Si coating. On the other hand, the Si2p peak shows two different evolutions: up to 1ML, the peak remains symmetric and located at 101.3eV, most of which comes from the SiC substrate. At the coverage of 3MLs, the appearance of two shoulders is observed. They are ascribed to new components: a SiO_x peak at 102.3eV and the Si bulk at 99.2eV. The intensity of these two components increases for a deposited thickness of 6MLs. This result is in good agreement with the formation of 3D islands observed by AFM and confirms that these islands are composed of bulk Si, which is usually covered by a native oxide of a few angstroms thickness after air exposure.

Figure 3: XPS spectra of Si thin films of different thicknesses from 0,125, to 0,25, 0,5, 1, 3, and 6MLs: (a) C1s and (b) Si2p core-level peaks.

Figure 4a displays the Raman spectra for Si layers with different coverages grown on the (6x6)Gr layer. The first-order asymmetric peak located at 520 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the SiC substrate. For small coverages ($< 1\text{ ML}$) two new peaks appeared: one at 560 cm^{-1} which is interpreted as the zone-center E_{2g} vibrational mode of Si-ene (equivalent to the so-called G-like peak of Gr), which was predicted by theoretical studies at 570 cm^{-1} ³⁴ and another at 240 cm^{-1} which is assigned to the breathing mode (a zoom of the two peaks is given in Figure 4a). A breathing mode at 230 cm^{-1} was already reported for Si-ene on Ag. It was correlated with the out-of-plane displacement of Si-atoms that is generated by the buckling.⁸⁰ Its intensity is affected by the quantity and nature (zigzag or armchair) of step edges in the Si-ene flakes and we can expect that a higher density of 2D Si-ene flakes produces a peak with higher intensity. In this series of experiments, its intensity slightly increases up to 0.5ML until it completely disappears at 1ML, as shown in Fig. 4b. A similar evolution is observed for the E_{2g} peak: it increases with coverage rate up to 0.5ML where it reaches its maximum, before it disappears at 1ML coverage. The absence of any silicon related Raman modes at high coverage ($>1\text{ML}$) suggests the oxidation of the silicon deposited on the surface. The two peaks are absent for larger coverages, meaning that Si-ene is only formed at small deposited thicknesses ($<1\text{ML}$). These results are in good

agreement with the AFM images of the surfaces (Figure 2) where 2D flakes are well visible until 0.5ML coverage, from which on they totally disappear. We can then conclude that the 2D flakes visible on the surfaces are composed of 2D quasi-free-standing Si-ene.

The increase of the E2G peak intensity until 0.5ML (Figure 4b) is most likely induced by an increase of the quantity of Si-ene. Nevertheless, with such low coverage rates (0.125, 0.25 and 0.5) and quite inhomogeneous deposition, it is very uncertain to give a quantitative estimate of the Si-ene coverage on the surface.

It is the first time that the E2g peak of Si-ene is observed at a frequency so close to the free-standing peak confirming the very low interaction of the Si-ene flakes with the epitaxial graphene. In addition, as we already reported, the E2g mode in 2D materials can also be modulated by strain and doping.³⁴ In the case of Si-ene on Ag, the E2g peak is located at 530cm^{-1} because of its strong interaction with the substrate which is obviously not the situation here.⁸¹ In the case of Si-ene nanosheets on highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) substrate, the E2g mode is located around 542cm^{-1} because of the relaxation of the Si-Si bond length due to removal of the periodic constrains for an infinite Si-ene layer with respect to the surface underneath .⁵¹

In addition, the Raman shifts of the E2g and breathing mode are reported in Figure 4c. It is worth noting that the breathing mode Raman shift remains at 240cm^{-1} for different silicon thicknesses, supporting the attribution to the out-of-plane displacement of silicon atoms⁸⁰, while the E2g Raman shift increases linearly with the silicon coverage from 558cm^{-1} (0.125 ML) up to 563cm^{-1} (0.5 ML). This is an indication that, with the enlargement of the lateral size of the Si-ene flakes, the interaction with substrates and Si islands at the periphery of the domains decreases leading the E2g Raman shift toward the freestanding value of 570cm^{-1} . The error bars reported in Fig 4b and 4c are obtained by statistical analysis of $20\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ Raman maps.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Raman spectra of Si/(6x6)Gr/6HSiC with 0,125, 0,25, 0,5, 1, 3 and 6ML coverage: (a) silicon vibrational range of the major Raman features of silicene. Asterisks denote the SiC Raman modes. Evolutions of the 2D Si-ene mode (b) intensity and (c) shift.

The evolution of the Raman spectrum of epitaxial graphene with increasing coverage of silicon is shown in Fig 5a. The main modifications of the graphene Raman modes are: the broadening of the 2D mode, as summarized in Fig. 5b, and the shift of the G and 2D modes. In particular, the 2D full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the 2D mode increases with the increase of the silicon coverage, going from 35 cm^{-1} for the 0.125 ML up to 38 cm^{-1} . The error bars reported in Fig 5b are obtained by statistical analysis of Raman maps obtained in a $20 \text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ sampling area. The broadening of the 2D peak is assigned to nanoscale strain effects on the graphene layers.⁸² Considering the low interaction of the Si-ene sheets obtained on the graphene surface, it is possible that the strain effects are induced by the presence of the dendritic structures, and in fact this effect dominates for the 3 ML and 6 ML coverages, where Si-ene is completely absent and a complete coverage with a dendritic layer is observed. A similar behavior is reported in the correlation plot of the Raman shift of the G peak with the one of the 2D mode (Fig 5c). The dispersions with different silicon coverages reveal that the n-type doping of epitaxial graphene slightly decreases, while an important spreading is present in all the set of data along the strain direction. This decrease of the electron doping concentration can be due to interface states of oxidized silicon at high silicon coverage.⁸³ The slope of the linear fitting for the different dispersions varies between 1.2 up to 1.7 that is an indication for biaxial strain of the graphene layer, which is expected due to the complex interaction between graphene and the dendritic structures.⁸⁴

Figure 5: Raman spectra of Si/(6x6)Gr/6HSiC with 0,125, 0,25, 0,5, 1, 3 and 6MLs coverages: (a) vibrational range of the major Raman features of graphene. (b) Evolution of the FWHM of the 2D mode as function of the silicon coverage. (c) Strain/doping correlation plot of epitaxial graphene with increasing silicon coverage.

To understand the reproducibility, homogeneity and the mechanism of formation of thin Si-ene areas surrounded by 3D dendrites better, various samples have been realized for a deposited thickness of 0.5 ML which produces the most extended 2D areas. After deposition, all samples showed evidence for large flakes of Si-ene (with a mean lateral size of some hundreds of nm) with compact almost hexagonal shapes surrounded by dendritic 3D islands (Fig. 6a). After 2h annealing at high temperatures (850°C), the density, size and shape of the 2D flakes do not evolve, but their edges become straighter following directions at 120° from each other, which further emphasizes their pseudo-hexagonal shape representative of higher quality crystalline flakes (Fig. 6b). The height of the compact planar areas remains in the range of 0.2 – 0.3nm after subtraction of the instrumental offset caused by different interaction forces. On some AFM images, it is also well visible that the Si-ene “floats” on top of the Gr substrate without interacting with it, as can be seen on figure 6c where a flake is straddling two terraces like a sheet laid on the step edge.

Figure 6: AFM images of the surface after 0,5ML Si deposition at RT: (a) just after growth; (b) after 2h annealing at 850°C; (c) AFM image of a Si-ene flake straddling two terraces. The corresponding STM images of this sample are presented in figure S3.

The initial steps of the Si-ene flake growth (2D domains followed by 2D domains with a ridge) may be perfectly rationalized by an epitaxial growth mode dictated by solid-state dewetting.⁸⁵ We show evidence for such a mechanism thanks to kinetic Monte-Carlo simulations of the epitaxial dynamics. We consider a model geometry with a Solid On Solid (SOS) model where the atomic columns are defined on the basis of the Gr honeycomb lattice. A constant deposition flux F allows the deposition of Si on Gr. Meanwhile, the top-most atoms are allowed to diffuse with a diffusion energy barrier E_S and to detach from their n nearest-in-plane neighbors with a bonding energy barrier E_N . In this case, the diffusion and detachment processes occur with a frequency proportional to $\exp[-\beta(E_S + n E_N)]$. Importantly, the energy barriers E_S and E_N are supposed to be function of the local height h . This is characteristic of wetting conditions where excess quantities depend on the local environment, and especially on the thickness here. This crucial assumption happens naturally here because the Si atoms on the first layer are only weakly bounded to the Gr layer via van-der-Waals interactions. On the contrary, Si atoms diffusing on top of already deposited Si atoms are expected to experience a greater energy barrier due to their covalent bonding with underlying Si atoms. These barriers are thence a priori function of the atomic height, until they reach their values on bulk Si beyond a given thickness (typically

beyond 3 or 4 monolayers).⁸⁶ The diffusion barrier of Si on Gr was computed to be as low as 0.06eV on the basis of ab-initio calculations.⁸⁷ It is indeed much lower than the usual diffusion barrier of Si on Si(001) that was measured to be 0.7eV.⁸⁸ The system is highly anisotropic and the dependence of E_N on h is less documented. However, for the special case of Si on top of Si(001) with anisotropic type-A and B terraces, it was typically estimated at 0.5eV by comparison of the results of such a SOS model with anisotropic experimental morphologies on Si(001).⁸⁹ We thence considered that E_S and E_N vary over $h=1$ and 2 and stay constant for $h \geq 3$. We fixed $E_S (h=1) = 0.06\text{eV}$ and $E_S (h \geq 3) = 0.7\text{eV}$ and considered typically $E_S (h=2) = 0.08\text{eV}$, while we set $E_N (h) = 0.4, 0.5$ and 0.6eV for $h = 1, 2$ and 3, respectively. The resulting evolution is displayed in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: (left) Morphologies of KMC simulations of a SOS-model with thickness-dependent diffusion E_S and binding energies E_N at room T for the typical parameters described in the text and for deposit Si amount $\theta = (a) 0.05, (b) 0.1, (c) 0.15, (d) 0.2, (e) 0.5$ and $(f) 2.0$ ML (the system size is 200×200 lattice parameters). (right) Evolution of the surface of the 2D flakes as a function of θ .

Initially, growth proceeds by the enlargement of a flake that remains perfectly flat and 2D (Figure 7a-c). From a typical deposit of θ^* , and for flake sizes of the order of 100 lattice parameters, a ridge starts to form on one edge of the flake. It is noticeable that this localized ridge perfectly corresponds to the geometries initially observed experimentally (Figure 2a). Once formed, the ridge quickly spreads over the entire flake edge and then thickens slowly. At $\theta=0.5\text{ML}$ (Figure 7e), the 2D zone with a thickness $h=1\text{ML}$ is entirely surrounded by a ridge that has a typical thickness of 2 to 3 ML, once again in accordance with the flakes observed experimentally. The precise values of θ where the latter steps occur depend on statistical fluctuations, but we observe that the ridge is usually fully formed at 0.5ML. As deposition proceeds, the 2D flake is gradually shrinking and the ridge progressively occupies the entire flake, as can be evidenced by the evolution of the 2D central zone in Figure 7e-f. We thence argue that the so particular flakes and ridges morphologies observed experimentally result from the epitaxial growth dynamics of 2D systems with dewetting conditions depicted by our model. The values of the energy barriers considered here are therefore adequate to account for the

experiments, and this result can be considered as a validation or at least an indication of their real values. Important variations of these barriers could, indeed, lead to other growth modes: a plane-by-plane growth; a fast dewetting leading to compact rough and thick shapes, etc. A detailed study of the different morphologies potentially contained by this model will be given elsewhere.

The above modelization is dedicated to the 2D flake and ridge formation and does not capture the dendritic growth that would require a full description of the Si aggregate growth. The mechanism of transition from 2D to 3D dendrites in MBE growth is poorly understood, even if in general it is correlated to the growth rate and deposition flux. Here the situation is very complex since Si is supposed to have a very high diffusion length on Gr even at RT,⁸⁷ and there is a huge anisotropy of interaction between the strong Si-Si lateral bonds and the weak interaction perpendicular to the surface. When the 2D compact domains reach a critical size, the rate at which the adatoms arrive at the domain edges becomes higher than the edge diffusion that becomes insufficient to ensure the rearrangement of all incoming adatoms to a stable geometrical configuration. This promotes the branching along the directions of the domain expansion, leading to dendritic Si domains. For this reason, the compact area will ramify into branched structures whose primary branches roughly follow a pseudo-hexagonal shape. For larger dendritic structures, with elongated branches, the adatoms agglomerate following a diffusion limited process which produces a thickening and disorientation of the branches and the 3D growth prevails. The structural transition can then be attributed to the difference between the rate of adatom attachment to the edge of the growing nuclei, the rate of edge diffusion and to the strong anisotropy of the Si-Si interactions between the lateral and the vertical ones. At increasing thickness, the morphology evolves with a densification and thickening of the 3D dendrites accompanied by an increase of their size. A comprehensive study on the growth mechanism of the 3D silicon dendrites will be the topic a future work.

CONCLUSION

Our results provide a clear proof and a complete explanation of the van der Waals epitaxy of 2D Si-ene flakes on (6x6)Graphene, when using ultra-clean MBE deposition technique and defect-free graphene substrate. The 2D Si-ene flakes are well identified on AFM images for low silicon deposition thickness (<1ML). The presence of 2D flat areas straddling two terraces like a sheet laid on the step, gives a first indication that the Si-ene flakes “float” on top of the Gr substrate without interacting with it. The 2D domains are surrounded and progressively covered by 3D ridges forming dendritic islands, that entirely cover the surface at the expense of the 2D flakes at 1ML deposition. The formation of large scale Si-ene flakes is also unambiguously attested by Raman spectra which evidence the vibration modes ascribed to Si-ene: the zone-center E_{2g} vibrational mode at 560 cm⁻¹, which was predicted by theoretical studies at 570 cm⁻¹ for free-standing Si-ene and the breathing mode at 240 cm⁻¹ which is correlated to the out-of-plane displacement of Si-atoms generated by the buckling.

The intensity of these two peaks (E2g and BM) which is related to the quantity of Si-ene flakes, increases up to 0.5ML where the peaks reach their maximum until they completely disappear at 1ML. The absence of these two peaks for larger coverages, indicates that Si-ene is only formed at small deposited thicknesses (<1ML).

The growth of the Si-ene flakes followed by 2D domains with a surrounding ridge is perfectly explained by Kinetic Monte-Carlo simulations when considering highly anisotropic barriers i.e. a factor 10 difference between the diffusion energy barrier (E_s) and bonding energy barrier (E_N). These barriers are also function of the atomic height, until they reach their values on bulk Si beyond a critical thickness (3-4ML). The first layer of Si atoms which is only weakly bounded to the Gr layer via van-der-Waals interactions has a very low diffusion barrier (set at 0.06eV on the basis of ab-initio calculations). On the contrary, Si atoms diffusing on top of already deposited Si atoms are expected to have a greater energy barrier due to their covalent bonding with the underlying Si atoms (0.7eV was measured on Si(001)). A similar height dependent evolution of E_N is also considered. In these conditions, it is shown that the growth proceeds by the enlargement of a flake that remains perfectly flat and 2D up to a typical deposited thickness, above which a ridge starts to form on the edge of the flake. Once the ridge is formed, it quickly spreads over the entire flake and then thickens slowly. The model demonstrates that the so particular flakes and ridges morphologies observed experimentally result from the epitaxial growth dynamics of 2D systems with dewetting conditions.

Our results elucidate the mechanism of formation of Si-ene and provide an efficient and simple way to produce high-quality and large-scale material. The work also opens the way to investigate quantum phenomena, topological insulator behavior towards reliable integration in devices with huge potential applications in nano-electronics, optoelectronics, and photonics.

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